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Decay channels of the ^{229}Th nuclear isomeric state involving atomic electrons

Pavlo Bilous and Adriana Pálffy

Max Planck Institute for Nuclear Physics, Heidelberg, Germany

In collaboration with

G. Kazakov, T. Schumm (Vienna University of Technology)

I. Moore (University of Jyväskylä, Finland)

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Nuclear energy levels of ^{229}Th

- ⇒ Nuclear frequency standard
V.V. Flambaum, PRL **97**, 092502 (2006)
- ⇒ Coherent control of nuclear transition via electron shell
W.-T. Liao *et al.*, PRL **109**, 262502 (2012)
- ⇒ Nuclear laser
E.V. Tkalya, PRL **106**, 162501 (2011)

Indirect measurement of the isomeric state energy

B. R. Beck *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **98**, 142501 (2007)

Attempt of a direct excitation of the isomeric state

No signal at
 7.8 ± 0.5 eV

⇒ We consider different
 values ΔE

J. Jeet *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **114**, 253001 (2015)

Internal conversion (IC)

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For M1-transition at $E \simeq 10$ eV
 γ -decay rate $\propto E^3$ is small
 $\Rightarrow \alpha$ is large

In neutral atom of ^{229}Th $\alpha \simeq 10^9$
L. v. d. Wense *et al.*, Nature 533 (2016)

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Ion charge	0	1+	2+	3+	4+
Ion. threshold (eV)	6.3	12.1	20.0	28.7	58

IC from excited states

Electronic states Th^+

IC from excited states

IC from excited states

IC from excited states

IC should be faster than radiative decay

A possible way to detect the isomeric state

- Prepare ions $^{229}\text{Th}^+$ in the nuclear isomeric state
- Excite the ions to a long-lived electronic state
- Separate and count produced ions Th^{2+}
- Carry out the same experiment for isotope ^{232}Th
- Compare results and find isomeric state contribution

P.V. Bilous, G.A. Kazakov, I.D. Moore, T. Schumm, and A. Pálffy
"Internal conversion from excited electronic states of ^{229}Th ions"
Phys. Rev. A, in press

Detection of isomeric state

Detection of isomeric state

IC from unique long-lived
electronic state of Th^+

$J = 3/2$, even

$J = 15/2$, odd

$J = 3/2$, even

$J = 15/2$, odd

State at 6213 cm^{-1}

- has one E1-channel
- photon energy is 45 cm^{-1}
- E1-decay rate is 10^{-4} s^{-1}

Further challenge

Experiment by I. Moore (University of Jyväskylä, Finland)

The end.

Thank you for your attention!

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